

Void detection in two-component annulus grout behind a pre-cast segmental tunnel liner using Ground Penetrating Radar

Brett Kravitz¹, Michael Mooney¹, Jurij Karlovsek², Ian Danielson³, Ahmadreza Hedayat¹

¹ *Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Colorado School of Mines, Golden, CO 80401, USA.*

² *School of Civil Engineering, The University of Queensland, Brisbane St Lucia, QLD 4072, AUSTRALIA.*

³ *Kiewit Corporation, Underground District, Omaha, NE, 68131, USA*

Corresponding Author: bkravitz@mines.edu

Keywords: GPR; two-component annulus grout; void detection; segmental liner; dielectric permittivity, electrical conductivity

ABSTRACT: Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) is being considered as a potential non-destructive technique for ensuring complete annulus grout backfill behind pre-cast segmental tunnel liners. Current methods for ensuring grout backfill involve drilled verification holes through the waterproof liner. The Rondout bypass tunnel, in Newburgh, NY, where void formation behind the tunnel liner is possible due to high groundwater pressures, provided an example project to evaluate GPR capabilities. While the application of GPR for void detection in one component grouts behind tunnel liners has been well-documented, site specific calibration of the GPR equipment and the application to two-component grouts is necessary. Experiments were conducted on actual tunnel segments to determine the most appropriate antenna frequency that can penetrate through the steel-reinforced segments and produce the best resolution. Mock air and water voids were embedded within areas of complete grout behind the segment to demonstrate the GPR signatures. Steel reflectors buried within the grout provided indirect measurements of the electromagnetic (EM) properties of the two-component grout. All field results were compared against analytical evaluation and numerical models to validate void detection. The findings of this research allow for direct implementation of the GPR technique for detection of voids behind segmental tunnel liners with two-component grout backfill.

1.0 Introduction

Verification of annulus backfill grout in TBM constructed tunnels is essential for the structural integrity and long-term performance of the tunnel lining. The current industry standard is to use destructive drilling methods through the pre-cast tunnel liner to verify there are not voids present. These methods are destructive to the water tightness of the liner and offer a limited look in the annulus. A non-destructive technique, such as ground penetrating radar (GPR) scanning, is sought to provide a reliable and efficient solution with broad coverage that can replace these destructive methods. The Rondout bypass water tunnel, in Newburgh, NY, with water pressures estimated to be as high as 26 bar in portions of the tunnel, provided an ideal project to evaluate the use of GPR for void detection in the annulus grout. High water pressures exerted on the annulus grout can induce grout washout and void formation in which detection is pertinent to perform secondary grouting to infill the voids. Use of GPR would further protect the water tightness of the tunnel liner by reducing the amount of penetrations made throughout the alignment.

Previous research has demonstrated the effectiveness of ground penetrating radar (GPR) to detect void anomalies behind reinforced-concrete tunnel linings (Lalague and Inge, 2010; Chen and Scullion, 2008; Parkinson and Ekes, 2008; Cassidy et. al., 2007; Davis et al., 2005). All of these studies involved the use of ordinary one component grout. However, the use of two-component grout with a sodium silicate accelerant has become common practice in recent tunnel projects and the two-component grout induces

greater GPR signal attenuation than ordinary grout (Azadi et al. 2017; Karlovsek et al. 2016; Zhang et al. 2010; Jain et al. 1983). Sodium silicate is a commonly used accelerant for grout and shotcrete applications along with aluminum sulfate (Azadi et al. 2017; Provis, 2017; Giannaros et al. 2016). High signal attenuation caused by the use of sodium silicate results in the inability for GPR to image beneath the grout and detect underlying voids.

Direct testing for the grout electromagnetic properties can be achieved in a laboratory using a vector network analyzer which can help predict the penetration depth and void signatures from a GPR signal. However, these tests are challenging and require the use of expensive specialized equipment. This study used field experiments to establish the void signatures expected in the annulus grout, verify which antenna frequencies can penetrate the double-matted steel rebar cage within the segment, and determine what depths GPR can penetrate through the two-component grout given the high signal attenuation. The results provide a basis for how GPR can be used to detect voids beneath a segment with two-component grout and the limitations of its application. The capabilities demonstrated can be implemented in a field environment with a reliable basis for anticipated results.

1.1 Project Background

The Rondout Bypass Tunnel project is an effort to replace a 4 km portion of the existing 137 km long Delaware aqueduct between Newburgh, NY and Wappinger, NY. Unrepairable structural damage to the original deep-rock tunnel has induced constant leaks of up to 130 million liters of fresh water a day. This aqueduct transports approximately 1.9 billion liters of fresh water a day, or half of New York City's fresh water supply (NYC Department of Environmental Protection 2016). Construction consists of two blasted shafts of 275 m and 200 m depths through shale on each side of the Hudson River with 267 m of water head possible along the alignment. A shielded-open face tunnel boring machine (TBM) will be launched through the western shaft and advance easterly underneath the Hudson River through a fractured limestone unit. Additional concern of hydraulic connectivity to the leaking Delaware aqueduct can induce water pressures greater than hydrostatic from the Hudson river above. Potential for annulus grout washout and rock excavation overcut leading to insufficient grout volume is of concern due to the highly fractured limestone underlying the Hudson River. Original construction efforts of the Delaware aqueduct between 1939 and 1945 demonstrated high water inflow rates while geotechnical investigations estimate inflows as high as 4.9 m³/min.

1.2 Rondout TBM

The TBM selected for the project is a single shield open-face TBM with a 6.6 m excavation diameter and sealable excavation chamber sufficient up to 30 bar of pressure. The pre-cast segmental liner installed inside of the TBM has an outside diameter of 6.2 m, which creates an annulus space of approximately 19.8 cm between the rock and the liner. A Two-component grout is to be continuously injected into the annulus space through the back of the tail shield as the TBM advances. Two-component grout, also referred to as A-B grout, is transported as separate components and mixed upon ejection into the annulus space, where it is designed to have a high early strength to support the weight of the TBM as it passes over the segments. Spring plates on the tail shield exterior and four sets of brushes on the interior are designed to prevent grout from back flowing into the TBM or into the excavation chamber. These brushes are capable of withstanding up to 30 bar of pressure. Six grout injection ports are located on the tail shield, two below the spring line and four above, one of which is depicted in Figure 1. Grout will be injected from four of the injection portals during production with each portal capable of approximately 110 L/min, for a total of 440 L/min into the annulus space.

Figure 1. Photo of Rondout TBM Tail Shield. Three rows of brushes shown on the upper left of the photo will fully encircle the inside of the shield. Spring plates shown on the bottom of the photo. One of six grout injection portals shown on the tail shield.

1.3 Expected Field Conditions

When the grout is first ejected from the ports, it flows as a low-viscous fluid. After approximately 15 seconds, the grout gels, forms a paste and stiffens with time. Its thixotropic nature implies the grout will return to a fluid-like state under sufficient applied pressure. This creates concern if high water flow rates or pressures exist in the annulus space, as was experienced in the original aqueduct construction, and does not allow the grout to properly set in place. The existence of poor rock mass with inter-connected fracture networks can potentially allow for washing of the grout out of the annulus space before it sets. This occurrence would lead to a large water filled void in place of the grout. A secondary effect of this type of void is for washout to continue as more grout is placed, leading to an insufficient grout volume and the potential for large voids to form at the crown. Another potential for void formation in the annulus space is for large rock-cut over break causing the grout to infill fractures within the rockmass and resulting in an insufficient grout volume. This would also cause a potential air or water filled void to form at the crown. Figure 2 provides illustration of the tunnel geometry and void formation possibilities. Void formation in the annulus space can lead to non-uniform stress distribution on the segmental tunnel liner which can then result in cracking of the concrete segments, reducing its water tightness (Henzinger et al. 2016).

Figure 2. Depiction of potential grout washout conditions. TBM trailing gear shown inside the tunnel.

2.0 GPR Background

GPR functions by emitting an electromagnetic (EM) wave pulse and measuring the return time and strength of the wave reflections off interfaces. When an EM wave reaches a differing material boundary, a portion of the wave energy will be reflected, and the remainder of the wave energy will transmit into the proceeding medium. An example is a wave traveling through concrete into water, where part of the wave reflects off the water boundary and part continues on through the water until reaching the next interface. The data collected by the transmitted EM wave pulse can indicate depth and type of boundaries and may be depicted in the form of a radargram, displayed in later examples. Comprehension on the physics of EM wave propagation is necessary for understanding and interpreting the results generated from a GPR radargram.

2.1 EM Wave Propagation

The principles for understanding GPR is founded in electro-magnetic wave theory. EM waves propagate according to a set of four mathematical equations known as the Maxwell equations (Annan, 2005):

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{e} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{b}}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{h} = \mathbf{j} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{d}}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{d} = \rho \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{b} = 0 \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{e} is the electric field strength vector (V/m); \mathbf{b} is the magnetic flux density vector (T); \mathbf{d} is the electric displacement vector (C/m²); \mathbf{h} is the magnetic field intensity (A/m); ρ is the electric charge density (C/m²); \mathbf{j} is the electric current density vector (A/m²); and t is time in seconds.

These equations describe orthogonally oriented changing electric and magnetic fields. Constitutive relationships between the parameters defined above and material properties describe how EM waves are affected by the medium in which they travel through. The three material properties are electrical conductivity (σ_T), dielectric permittivity (ϵ_T), and magnetic permeability (μ). For the materials described herein, the relative magnetic permeability will be assumed to be 1 (Annan, 2005; Knight and Endres, 2005) and therefore not considered to affect the EM wave propagation.

2.2 Dielectric Permittivity and Electrical Conductivity

EM wave propagation through a medium is dictated by two sets of complex equations containing four material properties (Knight and Endres, 2005):

$$\epsilon_T(\omega) = \epsilon'_T(\omega) - i\epsilon''_T(\omega) \quad (5)$$

and

$$\sigma_T(\omega) = \sigma'_T(\omega) - i\sigma''_T(\omega) \quad (6)$$

where $\epsilon_T(\omega)$ and $\sigma_T(\omega)$ are the total permittivity and total conductivity, respectively. $\epsilon'_T(\omega)$ is the dielectric polarization term, $\epsilon''_T(\omega)$ represents energy loss due to polarization lag, $\sigma'_T(\omega)$ refers to ohmic conduction, and $\sigma''_T(\omega)$ is related to faradaic diffusion, all as a function of frequency (Knight and Endres, 2005). Modeling the GPR signal requires knowledge of these parameters in order to determine the anticipated loss tangent:

$$\tan\delta = \frac{\sigma' + \omega\epsilon''}{\omega\epsilon' + \sigma''} \quad (7)$$

where $\tan\delta$ is the ratio of energy lost to energy stored. Materials with large loss tangents are commonly referred to as lossy materials, such as salt water. Stored energy from dielectric polarization is due to molecular, ionic, or atomic polarization when an electric field temporarily rotates and aligns either the molecules, ions, or atoms in a material, depending on frequency and material susceptibility (Knight and Endres, 2005). Energy losses typically come from either conduction due to electrical charge carriers present in a material or polarization lag from the EM frequency (Knight and Endres, 2005). Conducting materials dissipate the propagating EM wave into electricity described by the diffusion equation. Polarization lag refers to the inability for part of an EM wave to polarize the material due to an out-of-phase polarization relationship. Due to the fact that only two terms are determined from laboratory measurements (Chen et al., 2014), these four properties are typically described by two effective parameters (Knight and Endres 2005):

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \epsilon' + \frac{\sigma''}{\omega} \quad (8)$$

and

$$\sigma_{eff} = \sigma' + \omega\epsilon'' \quad (9)$$

where effective permittivity (ϵ_{eff}) and effective conductivity (σ_{eff}) describe the total energy stored and lost in a material, respectively. Effective permittivity in this report is considered to be the relative effective permittivity, where the values denoted are the real-valued effective permittivity divided by the permittivity of free space ($\epsilon_0 = 8.85418782 \times 10^{-12}$ F/m). Using these effective parameters reduces the loss tangent to:

$$\tan\delta = \frac{\sigma_{ef}}{\omega\varepsilon_{ef}} \quad (10)$$

Further simplifications are commonly made depending on the frequency range being analyzed. For frequencies above 100 kHz, σ''/ω may be assumed to be 0, and σ' is assumed to be equivalent to the DC conductivity, σ_{DC} . Hence, effective permittivity is approximated as the real component of the complex permittivity function and effective conductivity is the sum of the DC conductivity and the imaginary part of the complex permittivity function:

$$\varepsilon_{eff} = \varepsilon' \quad (11)$$

and

$$\sigma_{eff} = \sigma_{DC} + \omega\varepsilon'' \quad (12)$$

These forms of the simplified effective permittivity and conductivity are used herein.

2.3 EM Wave Assessment

Effective permittivity and conductivity determine EM wave velocity, impedance, and attenuation. All of these properties are essential to understanding the results from GPR scans since they effect the return time of a reflected wave off an interface, the amount of energy reflected from that interface, and the amount of energy lost as the wave travels through the material. The attenuation constant provides a basis of understanding for the depth a GPR wave can propagate for a given material at a specific frequency (Daniels, 2004):

$$\alpha = \omega \sqrt{\frac{\mu \cdot \varepsilon_{eff} \cdot \varepsilon_0}{2}} \cdot (\sqrt{1 + \tan\delta^2} - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (13)$$

where α is expressed in dB m⁻¹. Taking the inverse of the attenuation constant provides a depth at which ~37% of the energy is attenuated due to material losses, referred to as skin depth (Oldenburg et al. 2017):

$$\delta = \frac{1}{\alpha} \quad (14)$$

Skin depth is a useful indication for the depth GPR will work in a lossy material. This equation reveals that materials with high loss tangents will have greater attenuation and smaller skin depth. This is particularly true for conductive materials such as salt water and the two-component grout being studied in which the skin depth is on the order of centimeters, shown in Table 1. Skin depth of a dried single component concrete or grout will be on the order of meters since the conductivity is relatively low, as shown in Table 1. However, attenuation due to a material's permittivity and conductivity is only one aspect of the total attenuation, with scattering being the other major source in earthen materials. Scattering is the result of small reflections off inhomogeneous material boundaries such as soil grains or rock fractures. Concrete will not experience the degree of scattering that a soil with large inclusions will since the grain size in concrete is relatively small compared to the wavelength for the EM wave applied. Therefore, attenuation in dried single-component grout or concrete is typically not of great concern when using GPR on a centimeter or several meter scale.

EM wave velocity is determined from the wave phase constant (Daniels, 2004):

$$\beta = \omega \sqrt{\frac{\mu \cdot \epsilon_{eff} \cdot \epsilon_0}{2}} \cdot (\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \delta} + 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (15)$$

and

$$v = \frac{\omega}{\beta} \quad (16)$$

where velocity (v) may be expressed in m/ns. Estimating the EM wave velocity for a given material enables prediction of received wave times off boundary reflections. The amount of energy reflected off a material boundary is determined by the contrast in material impedance (Daniels. 2004):

$$\eta = \sqrt{\frac{-j\omega\mu}{\sigma_{eff} - j\omega\epsilon_{eff}\epsilon_0}} \quad (17)$$

where η is the complex intrinsic impedance of the medium measured in Ohms. A material with a large impedance implies a small permittivity. Therefore air, with a relative permittivity of 1, will have a relatively large impedance. Alternatively, a material with very large permittivity, such as water, will have a smaller impedance. Conducting materials, such as metals, will have an impedance approaching 0, indicating EM waves will be fully reflected. Reflection coefficients are then determined by (Daniels, 2004):

$$R = \frac{\eta_2 - \eta_1}{\eta_2 + \eta_1} \quad (18)$$

where η_1 is the impedance of the material in which the wave is propagating through, and η_2 is the impedance of the material at the boundary which the EM wave reaches. The reflection coefficient, R, can be negative or positive. The magnitude of the reflection coefficient indicates how much of the EM wave energy reflects off the boundary, where 0 indicates no impedance contrast, and 1 implies full reflection of the wave. Larger reflection coefficients indicate more energy is reflected off the interface and less energy is transmitted. A positive reflection coefficient indicates the wave has reflected off a material with a greater impedance, and the returned signal will maintain its incident phase. An example is a wave traveling through concrete and reflecting off an air boundary. Alternatively, a negative reflection coefficient indicates the wave has reflected off a material with a lower impedance, and the returned signal will reverse its incident phase. An example of this is an EM wave traveling through concrete and reflecting off water. Dielectric property values of common geomaterials are presented in Table 1 (Annan, 2005; Soutsos, et al. 2001).

Table 1. Dielectric properties of common geomaterials

Material	ϵ_{eff}	σ_T (mS/m)	v (m/ns)	α (dB/m)
Air	1	0	0.30	0
Distilled Water	80	0.01	0.033	2e-3
Fresh Water	80	0.5	0.033	0.1
Sea Water	80	3000	0.01	103
Dry Sand	3-5	0.01	0.15	0.01
Saturated Sand	20-30	1-10	0.06	0.03-0.3
Limestone	4-8	0.5-2	0.12	0.4-1
Shales	5-15	1-100	0.09	1-100
Silts	5-30	1-100	0.07	1-100
Clays	5-40	2-1000	0.06	1-300
Granite	4-6	0.01-1	0.13	0.01-1
Dry Salt	5-6	0.01-1	0.13	0.01-1
Ice	3-4	0.01	0.16	0.01
Concrete	5-12	0.01 - 100	0.10	0.01-6

3.0 Antenna Selection and Calibration

Experiments were conducted to select an antenna frequency with the best combination of penetration depth and resolution through the Rondout segments. Additionally, these results provided indirect means for inferring the EM wave velocity in the segment. Unknown dielectric properties of the segment concrete combined with additional attenuation caused by inhomogeneity's within the concrete makes direct penetration testing a necessity for GPR frequency selection. Therefore, numerical models provide aide in interpreting results but do not allow for determining directly the best frequency for the application. At a threshold minimum frequency, the wavelength may become too large to pass through the rebar cage or resolution may be too poor to detect voids, whereas at a maximum threshold frequency, steel reinforcement and high strength concrete will attenuate the signal before returning to the receiver.

3.1 Materials

Penetration depth experiment materials included GPR equipment with antenna frequencies of 400, 800, 900, 1200, 1600, and 2600 MHz, a pre-cast concrete segment from the Rondout project supplier, and a steel plate. The selected frequency range was based on anticipated permittivity of the materials being scanned, and literature review of past projects (Hee, 2012; Zhang et al. 2010; Parkinson and Ekes, 2008; Cassidy et al. 2007; Xie et al. 2007). As a general rule, the higher the frequency antenna, the shallower the penetration depth and the greater the resolution. The segment tested had a 67.25-degree arc with 3.1 m outer radius, 33 cm thickness, and 152 cm width, matching the dimensions of the segments used in production on the Rondout project. A double layer rebar cage with similar rebar spacing to production segments was provided but missing some of the cross supports on the ends of the segment. Two rebar layers separated by approximately 19.5 cm and embedded 3.8 cm in the segment formed a variable grid array with rebar spacing between 13.4 cm and 21.6 cm. Rebar diameters included 15.7 mm, 15.17mm, and 13.75 mm. An image of the rebar cage inside the tested segment is displayed in Figure 3. The segment was supported on a specially constructed wooden support frame, shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Steel rebar cage inside of segment used for antenna selection testing

The steel plate used to act a perfect reflector behind the segment was 6.35 mm thick, 203 mm wide, 356 mm long.

3.2 Test Procedure

GPR penetration tests were performed by moving the GPR antenna across the segment intrados with a steel plate held in contact with the segment extrados. The steel plate was held flush against the segment directly beneath the GPR scan line, as depicted in Figure 4. Each of the antennas described above was tested to see if the steel plate was apparent in the GPR scans. Resolved radar grams were compared to numerical model simulations to further validate the results and help resolve the effective velocity through the segment.

Figure 4. Picture of the segment on top of support frame used for penetration depth testing.

3.3 Penetration Test Results

GPR radargram results from the field penetration tests through the segment are displayed in Figure 5 (a-d). These radargrams are visual representations of hundreds of individual EM wavelets combined to create a 2-D rendering. The vertical axis is displayed in time units demonstrating the time a returned wave was received by the GPR unit, and the horizontal axis is real distance along the scan-line. White bands represent peaks of returned signals and black represents troughs. In other radargrams of this report, blue is used to indicate peaks and red used to indicate troughs. Filters were applied to the data sets in order to aid interpretation including time zero, bandpass, and time gain filters.

Radargrams provide a basis of interpretation to demonstrate the depth of rebar and which antenna frequencies enabled imaging of the steel plate. Six to seven parabolas are evident at approximately 1 ns on each of the radargrams and can be interpreted as the primary steel rebar layer in the segment. Point reflectors in a GPR scan appear as parabolas because as the GPR antenna moves towards or away from the point reflector, some of the spreading wave front will reflect off the point but be returned to the receiver at a later time. Shadowing effects, caused by the inability of an EM wave to propagate through steel, combined with an interference pattern from the first layer of rebar masks the second layer of rebar directly beneath.

The steel plate reflections and adjacent air reflection appears at approximately 7-9 ns on the 900 and 800 MHz radargrams. The steel plate reflection tapers off as the antenna is moved away from the plate and on top of air due to the same effect that generates the parabolic reflection from steel rebar. Reflections beneath the segment display a slight wavy nature which can be attributed to shadowing and refraction effects from the EM wave passing through the steel rebar cage. The phase reversal was evident for the steel plate as demonstrated by a slight time-offset in the reflection bands. The reflection time of the steel plate is a two-way travel time, therefore the effective EM wave velocity through the segment can be determined from half that time divided by the segment thickness. This resulted in an apparent velocity of ~ 0.1 m/ns. GPR waves with frequencies above 900 MHz did not demonstrate clear ability to penetrate through the segment and return reflected signals.

Other linear features displayed in the radargrams may be interpreted as background noise. Means of noise reduction are possible through background removal filters but these tend to also eliminate the air and steel plate reflections. Background noise is common in most radargrams at times greater than when the original EM pulse has attenuated.

Figure 5 Radargrams from four selected antennas on the steel plate penetration test. (a) 1600 MHz antenna; (b) 1200 MHz antenna; (c) 900 MHz antenna; and (d) 800 MHz antenna

3.4 Numerical Model

Numerical modeling was used to aide in interpretation of the GPR scan results. Models provide an example of the steel plate reflection if the signal were to pass through the segment. These models are unable to predict segment penetration without prior knowledge of the segment's electrical conductivity. Furthermore, additional signal attenuation is caused by scattering from inhomogeneities within the segment that cannot be captured in the model.

Numerical modeling of the penetration tests was performed using GPRMax open source software (Warren et al. 2016). This software solves Maxwell's equations in 3D using Finite-Difference Time-

Domain (FDTD). Modeling the GPR setup provided additional support for radargram interpretation. Model parameters included a maximum discretization of at least ten times smaller than the shortest expected wavelength (based on material permittivity and selected frequency), and beginning the simulated scans at least 15 cells from the boundary in order to minimize effects of the software absorbing boundary conditions (Giannopoulos, 2012). The model displayed in Figure 6 features a 900 MHz frequency antenna with receiver spacing matching that of the 900 MHz antenna used. An effective permittivity of 10 was used for the segment, which was chosen to match the field results for reflection time of the steel plate. This permittivity is within the high end of the concrete permittivity spectrum found in the literature (6-10) due to the high strength concrete used and the effects of the rebar cage refracting the signal. An assumed electrical conductivity of 0.1 mS/m was used matching values found in the literature (Zhang and Huang, 2010; Daniels, 2004). Steel rebar was not modeled in GPRMax because it convolutes the results with steel interference patterns without aiding in the interpretation. This model was solely intended to demonstrate the phase reversal between reflections off of steel versus air and to illustrate the steel plate reflection shape.

The numerical model in Figure 6 (a-d) demonstrates two key features from the steel plate. First is a phase reversal of the original wavelet from the reflection off steel compared to the in-phase reflection caused by air. This phase reversal can be identified by the reverse coloring of the reflection band between 7 to 8 ns on the left side versus the right side of the radargram in Figure 6b. Single traces of EM wavelets are plotted in Figures 5 c-d demonstrating the phase reversal of wavelets between reflections off steel versus air, respectively. Phase reversal can sometimes be identified in the field results by an apparent time offset in the reflection bands when signal background noise is prominent. The second key feature identifying the plate is the parabolic reflection shape of the steel plate as the GPR antenna moves away from the plate and directly over air. The shape of the steel plate reflection demonstrated in this numerical model matches the field results for the 900 and 800 MHz scans, while no such feature is visible in the higher frequency scan lines.

Figure 6 900 MHz numerical model (a) Geometry of model (b) GPRMax radargram results; (c) single trace at a distance of 10 cm, reflection off steel; (d) single trace at a distance of 80 cm, reflection off air

4.0 Void Detection and Grout Penetration

Anticipated tunnel conditions were emulated using two pre-cast segments supported on specially designed wooden frames. Divided compartments under the segment were backfilled with grout, water or air to simulate different possible scenarios. Objectives for this experiment were to (a) demonstrate the key GPR

signatures of different void types and (b) determine the grout's EM properties based on reflection results and their variations with the set time.

4.1 Materials

4.1.1 Support Frames

Wooden support frames were constructed to elevate the segments off the ground and create four sealed compartments. Gravel was spread inside the frames at the approximate curvature of the TBM rock cut and covered with plastic sheeting to ensure grout did not seep into the gravel and mask the grout-gravel boundary. Two separate frames were built, as shown in Figures 7a and b, to allow for a total of four different scan lines. The void spaces could be left empty with air or filled with water to demonstrate the different void signature types. Scan lines are depicted in Figures 7a and b as the orange dashed lines labeled A1, A2, B1, and B2.

Figure 7 (a) Support frame A plan view, profile view, and cross section (b) Support frame B plan view, profile view, and cross section

Segment support box A provided three different scan lines; a fully grouted annulus (A1), a water-filled void (A2-water), and an air-filled void (A2-air). The two outer and one central compartment in box A was filled with grout, while the remaining central compartment was left empty to be filled with air or water.

Segment support box B provided additional scan lines with the two outside compartments completely grouted, and shelves installed on the two center compartments with grout placed in between the shelf and the segment extrados. This enabled a 2.5 cm grout layer (B1) and 5 cm grout layer (B2) in contact with the segment and a water or air-filled void beneath. The two grout thicknesses were designed to demonstrate GPR signatures from varying grout thickness that may form in contact with the segment with

a void behind. Additionally, rebar was embedded within the grout compartment at varying depths to act as perfect reflectors to provide evidence of GPR penetration depth and grout EM velocity. Rebar was positioned at depths of 2.5 cm, 5 cm, 10.2 cm, and 20.3 cm beneath the segment, spaced approximately 20 cm apart from each other and positioned such that each rebar in the grout was radially centered in the segment's steel rebar grid. This prevented shadowing effects of the segment's rebar falsely masking the rebar in the grout. The rebar in the grout was meant to provide additional evidence for the grout attenuation constant as well as to help estimate the grout EM velocity.

4.1.2 Grout

Two-component grout was prepared by mixing component A in a colloidal mixer, comprised of water, cement, bentonite, and a retarder with an approximately 2:1 water to cement ratio. Retarder is used to keep component A in a stable liquid form for an extended period. The sodium silicate accelerant (component B) was pumped in separately at a controlled volumetric flow rate. After component B is mixed with the component A, the grout gels in approximately 15 seconds forming a low-strength semi-solid and gradually gaining strength over time. After 1 hour, the grout will stiffen to approximately 344 kPa unconfined compressive strength.

4.1.3 GPR

GSSI GPR equipment was used for the grout and void assessment. Following the results from the segment penetration tests, a 900 MHz antenna was used. The same GPR was used for the secondary scans conducted 3 weeks after the initial scans.

4.2 Material Properties

Assumed electrical properties from literature review (Daniels 2004) as well as properties back-checked from the actual GPR scans are shown in Table 2. The permittivity of the concrete segment was estimated from the results of the penetration tests in order to match the two-way travel time through the segment. The anticipated conductivity of the grout was based on laboratory results from Karlovsek et al. (2016) for early set time. The high anticipated conductivity of the grout results in a skin depth of less than 1 inch. The electrical conductivity of the water was measured in a geotechnical study for the Rondout project.

Table 2 EM properties of materials in scan lines

Material	ϵ_{eff}	σ_T (mS/m)	v (m/ns)	δ (cm)	$ \eta $	$2t$ (ns)
Concrete	10	0.1	0.10	1.7×10^4	119	6.96^1
Grout	62	4420	0.03	1.11	36.3	12.5^2
Air	1	0	0.30	∞	377	1.35^2
Water	81	55	0.03	86.8	41.9	12.2^2
Gravel	2	0.1	0.17	9.2×10^3	218	-
Limestone	8	1	0.11	3.0×10^3	133	-

¹Two-way travel time through 33 cm (segment thickness)

²Two-way travel time through 20.3 cm (annulus thickness)

Based on the impedances shown in Table 2, reflection coefficients at each possible material boundary were tabulated in Table 3. Reflection coefficients are dependent on which direction the EM wave is traveling when reaching the material boundary, with opposite directions having opposite signs of the coefficient. This table can be used to evaluate the relative amplitudes for the reflected signals off different interfaces, with a coefficient of 1 being the greatest amount of reflected energy. As shown in Table 3, an EM wave traveling through air and reflecting off water would provide a coefficient of -0.8, which indicates a relatively large amount of energy is reflected and the returned signal will have a phase reversal. Whereas an EM wave traveling through water and reflecting off grout will provide a coefficient of 0.251, which indicates a relatively smaller amount of reflected energy and no phase reversal.

Table 3 Reflection coefficients for materials in scan lines with potential boundaries

		Material 2				
		Air	Water	Concrete	Grout	Limestone
Material 1	Air	0	-0.80	-0.63	-0.84	-0.48
	Water	0.80	0	0.48	0.25	0.52
	Concrete	0.63	-0.48	0	-0.58	0.06
	Grout	0.84	-0.25	0.58	0	0.62
	Limestone	0.48	-0.52	-0.06	-0.62	0

4.3 Test Procedure

The segment support frames were constructed and the segments placed on top as shown in Figure 8 (a-c). One cubic meter of grout component A was mixed in a colloidal mixer and then moved to an agitator tank for two hours. This emulates conditions experienced on the TBM since grout will typically take a minimum of two hours to be transported from the batch plant into the annulus gap. Component A set time has effects on the set properties of the final product as the free water content in the mix declines over time. The component A pump and the accelerant pump were attached to volumetric flow meters and piped into a wye connection with a 122 cm pipe outlet, also emulating the Rondout TBM mixing pipe length. Volumetric flow rates of the Component A and the accelerant were dialed to produce the Rondout project mix design. Component percentages were achieved by first pumping component A into an empty container until producing a steady flow rate, then dialing in the accelerant pump to meet the mix design. After grout was observed to properly gel the pipe was inserted into the grout compartments and filled individually. Grout filling took approximately 2 hours total to complete.

Figure 8 Photos of constructed support frames (a) Support frame A; (b) Support frame B; (c) Scanning segment on support frame B with 900 MHz antenna

After the compartments were grouted, GPR scan lines were conducted. The earliest scan line was conducted approximately 12 hours after grout was placed, representing the time between grout placement and scanning in the TBM. GPR scans were initially tested with air filled voids that were then filled with water so that water was in contact with the bottom of the segment. GPR scans using the 900 MHz antenna were re-performed after 3 weeks.

4.4 Void Detection

Radargrams from 900 MHz GPR imaging of support box A are presented in Figure 9 along with geometry of the scan line cross sections. Time zero, bandpass, and range gain filters were applied to the radargrams. The color scheme displayed used a selected amplitude threshold such that the positive white peaks turn to blue, and the negative black peaks become red making high amplitude reflections more easily identifiable. This enables differentiation between reflections off of different material boundaries.

The segment-grout interface is revealed as a linear reflection band between 7 and 12 ns in Figure 9a due to the uniform segment thickness and constant EM velocity. Shadowing effects from the rebar created a wavy pattern in the returned signal. The segment/water interface from the water void in Figure 9b reflects the EM wave at approximately the same amplitude, phase, and time as the segment-grout interface, therefore making the two primary reflections indistinguishable. This is due to the reflection coefficient of the concrete-grout and concrete-water boundaries being similar, shown in Table 3. However, because water has a significantly lower electrical conductivity, the EM wave is able to travel through the full water thickness and reflect off the gravel boundary behind it. This creates the reflected signal between 21-23 ns. This reflection is strong because the impedance contrast between water and gravel is large and water allows for a sufficient amount of EM energy to pass through without significant attenuation. The lack of a strong reflection beneath the grout reflections (Figure 9a) is the first line of evidence that the GPR signal was unable to penetrate the grout thickness.

Air voids leave a different signature than the water voids due to the difference in impedance between water and air. Air voids are distinguished by their in-phase reflected wave compared to the phase reversal of the grout reflection. The phase difference is demonstrated in Figure 9c by the reversal in color bands between 7 and 12 ns at the void location. The secondary reflection at the bottom of the air void occurs approximately 1.35 ns after the primary which makes the secondary reflection indistinguishable from the primary, unlike the late arriving strong reflection in the water void. As is commonly observed in air voids of small thickness relative to wavelength, the two reflected waves off the top and bottom of the void combine with each other to induce positive interference which increases the amplitude of the returned EM signal and amplifies the strong reflection on the radargram (Chen and Scullion, 2008; Nobes, 2016).

GPRMax numerical models were run to create idealized radargrams to compare against the field data. Material properties used in the model are displayed in Table 2 and the model geometry is shown in Figures 9 (a-c). Wooden structural supports in the support frame were not modeled to create simplicity in understanding the different void signatures. Similarly, rebar in the segment was not included in the models in order to clearly represent void signatures without convoluting the results with interference patterns, as was the case with the penetration test model.

Numerical models can be interpreted similarly to the field results with more clearly identified reflections and lack of background noise. The reflection coefficient between the segment and grout is negative which indicates a phase reversal illustrated on the model by the negative (red) central peak of the returned signal shown in Figure 9a. The second reflection shown by the model between 14-16 ns can be interpreted as a duplicate of the first reflection due to the commonly observed ringing effect. Ringing is caused by the reflected EM wave from the grout interface bouncing off the air as it returns to the surface and then reflecting off the grout interface a second time. Ringing was not as evident in the field results due to the addition of background noise and greater signal attenuation. Another line of evidence that this apparent reflection is due to ringing is that this reflection shows up uniformly in all the models regardless of void type present. Numerical models presented the same void signatures for the air and water voids as the field results, shown in Figures 9 (b-c). However, the air void model did not produce the interference effect observed in the field tests. Instead it produced separate arrival bands for the primary and secondary air void reflection.

Figure 9 Results from the field test experiment with the scan line geometry on top, GPR radargrams in the middle, and numerical model results on the bottom (a) Scan line A1 with complete grouting (b) Scan line A2 with water void (c) Scan line A2 with air void

4.5 EM Penetration through Grout

GPR results along scan line B1 after 12-hour and 3-week grout set time are displayed in Figures 10 a and b, respectively. The 12-hour set time grout resembles the fully grouted scan line A1 from Figure 9a, where no clearly identifiable features are demonstrated below the concrete-grout reflection band between 7 to 12 ns. The lack of any parabolic reflections from steel is indicative that the EM signal was unable to penetrate through any thickness of grout at the 12-hour set time. Similarly, the air void beneath the 2.5 m grout thickness was not discernable with a phase-shift or strong reflection that was evident in Figure 9c.

Scan line B1 after 3-week grout set time, shown in Figure 10b, demonstrated evidence of partial EM wave penetration through the grout. The segment-grout reflection band between 7 to 12 ns is less intense and interrupted by subtle parabolic features. The loss of intensity of this reflection is demonstrated by the lack of the thick white linear band at approximately 11 ns displayed in the 12-hour radargram. The subtle parabolic features between 0.4 and 0.9 m and at times greater than 11 ns can be inferred to be the steel rebar reflections. These features are more easily identifiable by comparison to the numerical model results also shown in Figure 10b. Based on an overlay of the numerical model with the field results, the steel reflections shown in the actual GPR scans are inferred to be rebar embedded at depths of 2.5 and 5 cm.

The air void buried beneath 2.5 cm of grout in the center of the scan line is not as evident as the air void demonstrated in Figure 9c but the air void interrupts the linear segment-grout reflection band similar to the rebar reflections. The right side of the scan line, between 1.9 to 2.5 m, provides the baseline conditions for full grout reflection with no interruption at the same set time (See Figure 10b).

Numerical model results are shown in Figures 10 a and b which used different values for the grout conductivity. A conductivity equal to 4500 mS/m is used to model 12 hours and 0.1 mS/m is used to model 3-week old grout. These conductivity values were selected to demonstrate a relatively high conductivity material as is expected for the grout at early set time based on lab testing results from Karlovsek et. al (2016), and a relatively low conductivity comparable to a dry concrete. Figure 10a, displaying model results with a relatively high electrical conductivity demonstrates a linear segment-grout reflection with neither the rebar nor air void beneath the grout identifiable. This result coincides with the observation from the field and represents a skin depth of less than 2.5 cm at a 12 hr set time. Figure 10b, with a relatively low electrical conductivity produces reflections for all four rebar within the grout, as well as the void reflection beneath the grout shelf. The rebar is displayed as parabolic-shaped reflections at times beyond 9 ns and distances between 0 to 0.7 m. The left most rebar is not as clearly identified since it is masked by the gravel reflection. The air void is identified immediately beneath the grout reflection and demonstrates a phase shift after the wave has passed through grout. Field results for the 3-week set grout displayed partial features from the low-conductivity model, indicating the actual conductivity of the grout after 3 weeks has decreased and enables a penetration depth ability of approximately 5 cm.

Figure 10 GPRMax models of scan line B1 with air and a 900 MHz frequency. (a) Grout electrical conductivity set to 4500 mS/m; (b) Grout electrical conductivity was set to 0.1 mS/m

5.0 Discussion

Complete grout washout within the tunnel annulus grout, as described in section 1.3 of this report, has been shown to be identifiable with a 900 MHz radar antenna and is both more likely than partial washout of grout and a more serious issue to identify in the field. Water and air voids at the interface of the segments revealed signatures that lesser-trained technicians could easily identify if the technology were to be deployed in the field. The main signature demonstrated by the water void was the reflection of dry gravel at the bottom of the water void. In-situ rock in the tunnel will be fully-saturated which would decrease the reflection coefficient at the water-rock boundary and make the void signature less strong than demonstrated here. However, the difference in impedance between saturated limestone and water produces a reflection coefficient of 0.522, shown in Table 3, which is still sufficient to create an identifiable water void signature. While not directly demonstrated from this testing, rock over break may be detected as similar to the air void signature with a parabolic feature (Lalague et al. 2016) if there is some air or water surrounding the rock over-break since the reflection coefficient between limestone and the segment is low.

Penetration tests through grout demonstrated that voids formed beneath a 2.5 cm thickness of grout may not be detectable with the GPR at set times less than 12 hours, but have the potential to be detected after a 3-week set time. The signature to observe in the field is a disturbance in the linear reflection pattern from a fully grouted annulus. This type of feature is most easily identified when scanned next to a region of complete grout.

Previous laboratory studies on the electrical conductivity of the grout demonstrated that the grout conductivity increased during the set time rather than decreasing (Karlovsek et al. 2016). For a single-component grout without chemical accelerants, as the free water content decreases due to the cement hydration process, the conductivity declines (Karlovsek et. al. 2016; Makul, 2013). When sodium silicate reacts with grout component A, an irregular glass structure is formed creating interstitial holes which allow for mobile sodium ion transport to conduct current (Tuller et. al., 1980; Martinsen, 1969; Klaus and Milberg, 1968). Results from this field experiment show that the grout electrical conductivity declines after 3 weeks. Detailed time studies of two-component grout electrical conductivity would determine the most appropriate time to scan in order to have the ability to detect voids beneath grout. However, since a 3-week set time did not enable complete penetration of grout beyond 5 cm, it is unlikely that any set time would. Inability to penetrate a GPR signal through more than 5 cm of two-component grout implies that the grout thickness and grout-rock interface may not be resolved.

The position at which GPR is conducted on a TBM will impact the GPR results since it has been demonstrated that the grout's electrical properties are affected by set-time. Complete washout of the grout can be detected at any point after grout injection, since the void signatures are evident while the grout is at early set time. Voids formed within or behind grout may only be detected after a sufficient set time, and therefore would require scanning be conducted further back on the TBM trailing gear.

6.0 Conclusion

Penetration testing using a range of GPR frequencies on a tunnel segment revealed that the highest frequency able to delineate a steel plate beneath the segment was 900 MHz. A mock-tunnel setup, composed of a segment elevated on a constructed wooden support frame with compartments of grout and void spaces, provided evidence that the 900 MHz antenna enables the best resolution for void detection. Complete washout of grout leaving a water or air void was demonstrated to match numerical model results and be clearly identifiable in the field. Water voids are distinguished between areas of grout by the secondary reflection between the water-rock interface at the bottom of the void. Air voids were distinguished by the phase-reversal and reflection intensity interrupting the linear grout reflection band. Therefore, GPR testing for void formation behind a concrete segmentally lined tunnel with two-component annulus grout is a sufficient non-destructive technique for determining regions of complete annulus grout washout.

High electrical conductivity of the grout was demonstrated from the inability to detect steel rebar or voids beneath 2.5 cm of grout after 12-hr set time. After a 3-week set time, some features buried 2.5 to 5 cm within the grout become identifiable to a well-trained GPR technician. High signal attenuation prevents grout-rock boundary detection. This implies that void formation in the tunnel may be undetectable if layers of grout form at the segmental liner interface and scanning can only be conducted at early set times. It is concluded that the sodium-silicate accelerant dominates electrical conductivity even after the grout has initially gelled and as it cures over time. Future laboratory testing is required to provide more detailed time-studies on the effects of two-component grout set-time on electrical properties.

7.0 Acknowledgments

Support of this research provided by Kiewit Corporation is greatly acknowledged. Ian Danielson and Niels Kofoed were of particular importance in completing this work.

8.0 Funding

This work was supported by the Kiewit Construction Grant.

Declaration of Interest: none

References

- Annan, A. P. 2005. "Ground-Penetrating Radar." In *Near-Surface Geophysics*, by Dwain K. Butler, 357-438. Society of Exploration Geophysicists.
- Azadi, Mohammad Reza, Ali Taghichian, and Ali Taheri. 2017. "Optimization of cement-based grout using chemical additives." *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering* 623-637.
- Cassidy, Nigel J., Rod Eddies, and Sam Dods. 2011. "Void detection beneath reinforced concrete sections: The practical application of ground-penetrating radar and ultrasonic techniques." *Journal of Applied Geophysics* 74: 263-276.
- Chen, Dar Hao, and Tom Scullion. 2008. "Detecting subsurface voids using ground-coupled penetrating radar." *Geotechnical Testing Journal* 31 (3).
- Chen, Z., M. Schwing, J. Karlovsek, N. Wagner, and A. Scheuermann. 2014. "Broadband Dielectric Measurement Methods for Soft Geomaterials: Coaxial Transmission Line Cell and Open-Ended Coaxial Probe." *International Journal of Engineering and Technology* 6 (5).
- Daniels, David J. 2004. *Ground Penetrating Radar 2nd Edition*. ISBN.
- Davis, Allen G., Malcolm K. Lim, and Claus Germann Petersen. 2005. "Rapid and economical evaluation of concrete tunnel linings with impulse response and impulse radar non-destructive methods." *NDT&E International* 38: 181-186.
- Giannaros, P, A Kanellopoulos, and A Al-Tabbaa. 2016. "Sealing of cracks in cement using microencapsulated sodium silicate." *Smart Materials and Structures* 25.
- Giannopoulos, A. 2012. "Unsplit implementation of higher order PMLs. Antennas and Propagation." *IEEE Transactions* (60 (3)): 1479-1485.
- Gregory, Andrew P., and R.N. Clarke. 2001. "Tables of the complex permittivity of dielectric reference liquids at frequencies up to 5 GHz." Teddington: National Physical Laboratory.
- Hee, Ivan A. 2012. *Use of Ground Penetrating Radar to Verify Segmental Lining Backfill Grouting*. Politecnico di Torino, Politecnico di Torino.
- Henzinger, Michael R, Nedim Radoncic, Bernd Moritz, and Wulf Schubert. 2016. "Back II of segmental lining – State of the art, redistribution behaviour of pea gravel, possible improvements." *Geomechanics and Tunnelling*.
- JA Underground. 2014. "Rondout West Branch Bypass Tunnel Construction and Wawarsing Repairs Project: Geotechnical Baseline Report." New York.

- Jain, H., N.L Peterson, and H.L Downing. 1983. "Tracer Diffusion and Electrical Conductivity in Sodium-Cesium Silicate Glasses." *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* 283-300.
- Kaatze, Udo. 2007. "Reference liquids for the calibration of dielectric sensors and measurement instruments." *Measurement Science and Technology* 967-976.
- Karlovsek, Jurij, Moritz Schwing, Zhen Chen, Norman Wagner, David J. Williams, and Alexander Scheuermann. 2016. "Dielectric measurement method for real-time monitoring of initial hardening of backfill materials used for underground construction." *Journal of Geophysics and Engineering* S19-S27.
- Klaus, Otto, and M. E. Milberg. 1968. "Ionic conduction in alkali and thallium silicate glasses." *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* 51 (6): 326-329.
- Knight, Rosemary J., and Anthony L. Endres. 2005. "3. An Introduction to Rock Physics Principles for Near-Surface Geophysics." In *Near-Surface Geophysics*, 31-70. ISBN.
- Lalague, Anne, and Hoff Inge. 2010. "Determination of space behind pre-cast concrete elements in tunnels using GPR." *13th International Conference on Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR)* (IEEE) pp. 1-5.
- Lalague, Anne, Matthew A. Lebons, Inge Hoff, and Eivind Grov. 2016. "Detection of Rockfall on a Tunnel Concrete Lining with Ground-Penetrating Radar (GPR)." *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering* 49: 2811-2823.
- Makul, Natt. 2013. "Dielectric Permittivity of Various Cement-Based Materials during the First 24 Hours Hydration." *Open Journal of Inorganic Non-Metallic Materials* 3: 53-57.
- Martinsen, William Edward. 1969. "Selected properties of sodium silicate glasses and their structural significance." Iowa State University.
- Nobes, David C. 2016. "Ground penetrating radar response from voids: A demonstration using a simple model." *International Conference of Ground Penetrating Radar*. Nanchang, China: IEEE.
- NYC Department of Environmental Protection. 2016. "New York City 2016 Drinking Water Supply and Quality Report." Gov. Report.
- Oldenburg, Doug, Francis Jones, Lindsey Heagy, Rowan Cockett, Thibaut Astic, and Sarah Devriese. 2017. https://gpg.geosci.xyz/content/GPR/GPR_fundamental_principles.html .
- Parkinson, Graham, and Csaba Ekes. 2008. "Ground Penetrating Radar Evaluation of Concrete Tunnel Linings." Birmingham, UK: 12th International Conference on Ground Penetrating Radar.
- Provis, John L. 2017. "Alkali-activated materials." *Cement and Concrete Research*.
- Soutsos, M. N., J. H. Bungey, S. G. Millard, M. R. Shaw, and A. Patterson. 2001. "Dielectric properties of concrete and their influence on radar testing." *NDT&E International* 419-425.
- Tuller, H. L., D. P. Button, and D. R. Uhlmann. 1980. "Fast ion transport in oxide glasses." *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* 40: 93-118.
- Warren, Craig, Antonios Giannopoulos, and Iraklis Giannakis. 2016. "gprMax: Open source software to simulate electromagnetic wave propagation for Ground Penetrating Radar." *Computer Physics Communications* 163-170.

Xie, Xiongyao, Yunjian Liu, Hongwei Huang, Jun Du, and Fengshou Zhang. 2007. "Evaluation of grout behind the lining of shield tunnels using ground-penetrating radar in the Shanghai Metro Line, China." *Journal of Geophysics and Engineering* (IOP) 4: 253-261.

Zhang, Fengshou, Xiongyao Xie, and Hongwei Huang. 2010. "Application of ground penetrating radar in grouting evaluation for shield tunnel construction." *Tunneling and Underground Space Technology* 25: 99-107.